

Suicide Risk Among the Octogenarian Age Group: A Comparative Study

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ABSTRACT

Objective: We aimed to investigate the factors that affect the likelihood of suicide in the elderly, with a focus on individuals aged 80 and older.

Method: This is a cross-sectional study conducted in 7 nursing homes in the Manisa province, Türkiye. The data has been collected through face-to-face using a socio-demographic data form, the life satisfaction scale, and the suicide probability scale. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics 26.0, non-parametric statistical methods have been employed.

Results: The study included 278 elderly participants, 5 outliers were removed from the analysis. Among the included elderly participants (n=273), the anger score averages of males were higher. Low, high, and moderate income were found to have a higher suicide probability respectively. Those who resided in a nursing home for 3 years or more had higher anger scores. Elderly individuals residing in publicly funded nursing homes had higher averages in suicide probability, negative self, exhaustion, and anger scores. Further analyses were performed among the octogenarian population (n=149). Octogenarian males had higher scores in Suicide Probability, Disconnection from Life, and Anger Scale than the female octogenarian participants. Octogenarians with low income were found to experience a lack of attachment to life and higher levels of anger. In publicly funded nursing homes, octogenarians had higher suicide probability and anger scores compared to those in private nursing homes.

Conclusion: The risk of suicide in octogenarians should be taken seriously. Factors such as gender, income level, and type of nursing home can influence this risk.

Keywords: Octogenarians, Suicide, Probability, Geropsychiatry, Aging

INTRODUCTION

In older adults, suicide is emerging as a significant public health concern in societies; however, due to the relatively shorter life expectancy and lower workforce contributions of the elderly, suicide of such individuals do not garner as much attention as those of adolescents or young adults (Crestani et al. 2019).

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines suicide as an act initiated by an individual in which they consciously undertake an action that they know or expect will have a lethal outcome (World Health Organization 1998). It has been reported that one person loses their life every 40 seconds due to suicide worldwide. This figure represents the annual global age-standardized suicide rate of 11.4 per a 100000

population (15 for males and 8 for females) (World Health Organization 2014).

Suicide among the elderly is a phenomenon that results from a complex interaction of psychological, social, and biological factors. Fundamentally, suicide rates increase with age, especially in industrialized countries, and the highest rates are observed among elderly males. Risk factors for suicide in the elderly include: advanced age, male gender, living alone, bereavement (especially in males), psychiatric illness (depression, alcohol misuse, prior suicide attempts, vulnerable personality traits), and physical illness (pain) (Cattell 2000). Elderly individuals are more likely to complete suicide compared to young individuals. Furthermore, research has shown that elderly individuals are more determined and less impulsive when they make suicide attempts compared to

How to cite: Cengiz C, Bölükbaşı S. (2025) Suicide Risk Among the Octogenarian Age Group: A Comparative Study. *Türk Psikiyatr Derg* 36:14. <https://doi.org/10.5080/u27354>

Received: 20.05.2023, **Accepted:** 14.10.2023, **Available Online Date:** 19.02.2024

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younger individuals (Fox et al. 2017). Any suicide attempt or action by an elderly individual should be taken highly seriously. The presence of multiple physical and mental illnesses increases the risk of suicide. Physical illnesses such as epilepsy, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and congestive heart failure, as well as mental health disorders such as anxiety, depression, and bipolar disorders, are particularly associated with high suicide rates (Juurlink et al. 2004). It has been reported that approximately 90% of individuals who attempt suicide have at least one diagnosable mental illness (Cattell 2000). Suicidal men more commonly resort to violent methods (e.g., hanging or firearms), while women are more likely to use overdose or self-poisoning methods (Shah and Buckley 2011).

Octogenarians (individuals aged 80 and over) particularly constitute a demographic group at risk for attempting suicide. The likelihood of suicide among octogenarians may also vary according to gender. Research indicates that suicide rates among male octogenarians are usually higher than those among females (Conwell et al. 2011). However, it has been found that suicide risk is also associated with other demographic factors, socioeconomic status, and living conditions (Conejero et al. 2018). Developing effective interventions to reduce suicide risk among octogenarians requires a multidisciplinary approach involving collaboration among mental health professionals, family members, and community leaders.

This research aims to contribute to a better understanding of the factors that influence suicide risk among octogenarians and to the development of strategies for preventing suicide in this age group. The strongest aspect of this research is that it improves the clinical awareness about octogenarians, one of the most vulnerable populations of the society, and geriatric suicides which is an important public health problem, thus establishing a reference point for studies to be conducted in the future. Therefore, it is believed that drawing attention to the 'octogenarian' group for the first time in the Turkish psychiatric literature and investigating suicidal ideation in this age group for the first time will make significant contributions to the international literature.

METHODS

This cross-sectional study was conducted in a total of 7 nursing homes, two of which are private, under the auspices of the Ministry of Family and Social Services in Manisa Province. Data were collected by researchers based on the responses provided by the participants through face-to-face interviews and stored via Google Forms. The stored data were encrypted and protected by the Norton 360 Antivirus Program and will be retained for a period of ten years.

The population of the study consists of 307 individuals aged sixty and over who reside in nursing homes in Manisa Province and do not have active or chronic psychopathology or infectious diseases. Although all the elderly individuals were intended to be included in the study, 278 of them agreed to participate. In accordance with the recommendation of International Business Machines Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Program (IBM SPSS Statistics) version 26.0, 273 individuals were used for analysis.

Voluntary participants who were cognitively capable of answering the questions and aged 60 and over, residing in any nursing home in Manisa Province for a minimum of 6 months, were included in the study. Individuals who did not complete the interview or did not agree to participate in the study were not included.

Ethical Remarks

This research was conducted in accordance with all the relevant guidelines of the Human Participation Monitoring Committee (HPMC), the Human Research Monitoring Board (HRMB), and the ethical principles outlined in the Helsinki Declaration. Participants were informed and their consent was obtained. The data collection forms did not include the names of the participants. Data obtained from the research will be used solely for scientific purposes and confidentiality will be maintained.

Ethical approval for the research was obtained from the Ethical Board for Non-Interventional Clinical Research of İzmir Katip Çelebi University on March 23, 2023, with Decision Number IRB0112-0125.

Data Collection

Three data collection tools were employed in the study. First, a questionnaire form was used to determine the socio-demographic characteristics of the elderly volunteers in the study. Secondly, the Satisfaction with Life Scale was employed to assess the life satisfaction of the elderly individuals. Lastly, the Suicide Probability Scale was administered to quantitatively assess the severity of self-harm thoughts in the elderly.

Demographic Data Form

It is the questionnaire form prepared to gather the information about socio-demographic characteristics of the volunteers willing to participate in the study.

Satisfaction with Life Scale

Diener and colleagues developed a valid and reliable measurement tool for assessing life satisfaction in 1985 (Diener et al. 1985). This measurement tool is a one-dimensional scale consisting of 5 items. The Turkish validity

and reliability study of the Satisfaction with Life Scale was conducted by Dağlı and Baysal (2016). The scale is scored between 5 and 25, and there is a positive correlation between the scores obtained and life satisfaction. Reverse coding is not applied (Dağlı and Baysal 2016).

Suicide Probability Scale

Cull and Gill developed the Suicide Probability Scale in 1990 to assess the potential suicide risk in adolescents and adults. This scale consists of a total of 4 subscales and aims to evaluate different dimensions, such as hopelessness, suicidal ideation, hostility, and negative self-evaluation. Each subscale is based on a different theoretical approach related to suicide. The Suicide Probability Scale is comprised of 36 items and answered on a 4-point Likert-type scale. Two types of scores are obtained from the scale, namely weighted scores and standardized T-scores: Accordingly, the total score obtained ranges from 36 to 144 (Cull and Gill 1990). With a modification made by Şahin and Batıgün in 2000, items 2, 6, 10, 11, 18, 20, 22, 26, 27, and 35 are reverse-scored. As a result of the factor analysis conducted on this scale, three factors were identified: "Negative Self and Burnout" (items 5, 9, 10, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 23, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 32, 33, 35, and 36), "Detachment from Life" (items 2, 6, 7, 11, 20, 21, 22, and 24), and "Anger" (items 1, 3, 4, 8, 13, 14, 31, and 34). According to the results of the discriminant validity analysis conducted, it was observed that the scale was able to correctly classify 87.3% of patients who attempted suicide, 52.4% of those diagnosed with depression, and 81.5% of healthy individuals. These findings support the scale's discriminant validity (Batıgün and Şahin 2018). The Turkish version of the scale was subjected to validity and reliability studies in community and clinical samples of individuals aged 14-76 by Atlı, Eskin, and Dereboy in 2009. The Cronbach's alpha value for the entire sample was found to be 0.89. For the subscales, reliability coefficients ranged from 0.70 to 0.89. Cutoff score was determined as 110 and above (Atlı et al. 2009). The results of this study demonstrated that the scale can be reliably and validly used.

Data Analysis Method

For the analysis of the quantitative data obtained, data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 26.0 software. In line with the objectives of the study; percentage, mean, and standard deviation values were determined based on the nature of the variables. Additionally, the relationship between variables was examined to determine whether a significant difference existed. A value of $p < 0.05$ was determined for statistical significance. Due to the non-normal distribution of scores obtained from the dependent variables, non-parametric statistical methods such as Spearman correlation test, Run (Swed-Eisenhart) test, Mann-Whitney U test, and Chi-square

test were used to examine differences between groups. The Kruskal-Wallis Test was employed for multiple comparisons between groups.

RESULTS

A total of 278 elderly participants were included in the study. According to the recommendation of IBM SPSS 26.0 software, 5 elderly participants with outlier data were excluded from the analysis for the Suicide Probability Scale and its subscales. The sociodemographic data of the elderly participants included in the study ($n=273$) are presented in Table 1.

According to this table, 64.1% of the elderly participants in the study ($n=273$) were male, with a mean age of 77.9 ± 9.5 and within the octogenarian ($n=149$) group, 66.4% were male, with a mean age of 86.8 ± 4.4 .

The analysis of normality values and percentage calculations for the Satisfaction with Life Scale, the Suicide Probability Scale, and its subscales were conducted based on the total number of participants ($n=273$) in the study. According to the analyses performed, participants' responses to the Satisfaction with Life Scale (Kolmogorov-Smirnov=0.125; $p < 0.001$), the Suicide Probability Scale (Kolmogorov-Smirnov=0.167; $p < 0.001$), and its subscales Negative Self and Burnout (Kolmogorov-Smirnov=0.181; $p < 0.001$), Detachment from Life (Kolmogorov-Smirnov=0.159; $p < 0.001$), and Anger (Kolmogorov-Smirnov=0.201; $p < 0.001$) displayed a non-parametric distribution.

The correlation between the Satisfaction with Life Scale and the Suicide Probability Scale was found to be significantly negative according to the Spearman test ($\rho = -0.65$; $p < 0.01$).

The correlation and test values achieved by comparing the scores obtained from the dependent variable scales with the independent variables for all elderly participants in the study are shown in Table 2. According to this table: For the independent variable gender and the dependent variable scores, a significant relationship was found only in the Anger subscale ($Z = -0.2$; $p < 0.05$). It was determined that the mean anger scores for males (10.7 ± 2.2) were higher than those for females (10.2 ± 2.0).

For the independent variable income level and the dependent variable scores, a significant relationship was found in the Suicide Probability main scale ($H = 7.1$; $p < 0.05$), as well as in the Detachment from Life ($H = 7.6$; $p < 0.05$) and Anger ($H = 18.5$; $p < 0.001$) subscales affecting this scale. It was found that the elderly with low income (57.4 ± 7.2), high income (56.4 ± 5.6), and moderate income (55.1 ± 6.0) had higher mean scores in the Suicide Probability main scale, respectively.

According to the Spearman correlation test for the independent variable length of stay in the nursing home and the dependent

Table 1. Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Elderly Participants

Characteristics	All Elderly Group		Octogenarian (≥80)		Other (<80)	
	N=273	%	N=149	%	N=124	%
Gender						
Female	98	35.9%	50	33.6%	48	38.7%
Male	175	64.1%	99	66.4%	76	61.3%
Age	77.9±9.5 (60-96)		86.8±4.4 (80-96)		70.4±5.3 (60-79)	
Income Level						
Low	75	27.5%	40	26.8%	35	28.2%
Moderate	170	62.3%	100	67.1%	70	56.5%
High	28	10.2%	9	6.0%	19	15.3%
Marital Status						
Unmarried	248	90.8%	133	89.3%	115	92.7%
Married	25	9.2%	16	10.7%	9	7.3%
Perception of Health						
Bad	22	8.1%	9	6.0%	13	10.5%
Moderate	182	66.7%	100	67.1%	82	66.1%
High	69	25.2%	40	26.8%	29	23.4%
Chronic Illness						
Yes	229	83.9% [1.5±1.3 (0-8)]	112	75.2% [1.3±1.3 (0-8)]	117	94.4% [1.7±1.1 (0-7)]
No	44	16.1%	37	24.8%	7	5.6%
Physical Disability						
Yes	33	12.1%	19	12.8%	14	11.3%
No	240	87.9%	130	87.2%	110	88.7%
Number of Children	1.9±1.3 (0-8)		1.9±1.2 (0-7)		2.0±1.5 (0-8)	
Type of Nursing Home						
Public	199	72.9%	109	73.2%	90	72.6%
Private	74	27.1%	40	26.8%	34	27.4%
Duration of Stay at Nursing Home (year)	4.1±4. (1-25)		4.5±3.8 (1-24)		3.8±4.1 (1-15)	

variable scales, a weak relationship was found between the Suicide Probability main scale (ρ : 0.2; $p < 0.05$) and the Anger subscale (ρ : 0.2; $p = 0.001$; $p < 0.001$). Therefore, based on the recommendation of the Run (Swed-Eisenhart) test, an analysis was performed by separating from the median (3) value ($Z = -2.4$; $p < 0.05$). The Mann-Whitney Test analysis revealed that the mean Anger scores of those who had stayed in the nursing home for 3 years or more (10.8 ± 2.3) were more significant than those who had stayed for less than 3 years (10.2 ± 2.0) ($Z = -2.7$; $p < 0.05$).

For the independent variable type of nursing home and the dependent variable scores, a significant difference was found in the Suicide Probability main scale ($Z = -2.5$; $p < 0.05$), as well as in the subscales Negative Self and Burnout ($Z = -2.0$; $p < 0.05$) and Anger ($Z = -3.8$; $p < 0.001$) which affect

the main scale. The mean scores for Suicide Probability, Negative Self and Burnout, and Anger were higher for those staying in public nursing homes compared to those in private nursing homes.

The study focused on the octogenarian group among the elderly participants, and more in-depth analyses were conducted. The correlation and test values achieved by comparing the scores this group obtained from the dependent variable scales with the independent variables are shown in Table 3. According to this table: In the octogenarian group, a significant difference was found between gender and the Suicide Probability main scale ($Z = -2.2$; $p < 0.05$), as well as in the Detachment from Life ($Z = -2.6$; $p < 0.05$) and Anger ($Z = -1.8$; $p < 0.001$) subscales which affect the main scale. It is noteworthy that males had higher mean scores than females in all three scales.

Table 2. Overall Scale Scores of Elderly Participants

Characteristics	Scales				
	Satisfaction with Life	Suicide Probability	Negative Self and Burnout	Detachment from Life	Anger
Gender ^a	Z=-0.7; p=0.5	Z=-0.9; p=0.4	Z=-0.4; p=0.7	Z=-0.7; p=0.5	Z=-0.2; p=0.04
Female	17.7±3.3	55.1±5.8	29.0±4.0	15.9±1.6	10.2±2.0
Male	17.3±2.8	56.3±6.7	29.5±4.5	16.1±2.0	10.7±2.2
Age ^b	S.rho=0.1; p=0.09	S.rho=-0.05; p=0.4	S.rho=-0.07; p=0.3	S.rho=-0.07; p=0.2	S.rho=0.02; p=0.7
Income Level ^c	H=0.7; p=0.7	H=7.1; p=0.03	H=1.2; p=0.6	H=7.6; p=0.02	H=18.5; p<0.001
Low	17.4±2.6	57.4±7.2	29.8±4.9	16.5±1.7	11.1±2.4
Moderate	17.6±3.2	55.1±6.0	29.1±4.1	15.9±1.9	10.1±1.9
High	16.9±2.7	56.4±5.6	29.2±4.0	15.6±1.7	11.6±2.4
Marital Status ^a	Z=-0.7; p=0.5	Z=-0.7; p=0.5	Z=-1.5; p=0.1	Z=-0.004; p=1	Z=-0.8; p=0.4
Unmarried	17.5±3.0	55.8±6.4	29.2±4.3	16.0±1.8	10.6±2.2
Married	17.0±2.7	56.8±6.9	30.7±4.6	16.1±2.1	10.1±1.7
Perception of Health ^c	H=5.3; p=0.07	H=2.0; p=0.4	H=0.7; p=0.7	H=3.1; p=0.2	H=5.8; p=0.06
Bad	17.1±3.4	56.5±5.9	28.5±4.1	16.3±1.6	11.7±2.6
Moderate	17.2±2.8	56.1±6.2	29.4±4.3	16.1±1.8	10.5±2.1
High	18.2±3.2	55.1±6.8	29.3±4.7	15.7±2.0	10.2±1.9
Chronic Illness ^a	Z=-0.9; p=0.4	Z=-0.7; p=0.5	Z=-0.4; p=0.7	Z=-0.4; p=0.7	Z=-1.6; p=0.1
Yes	17.0±2.9	54.8±6.0	28.5±3.7	15.8±1.9	10.4±2.5
No	17.5±3.0	56.0±6.5	29.4±4.4	16.1±1.8	10.5±2.1
Physical Disability ^a	Z=-0.8; p=0.4	Z=-0.9; p=0.4	Z=-0.7; p=0.5	Z=-0.7; p=0.5	Z=-0.9; p=0.4
Yes	17.3±2.9	54.8±6.0	28.5±3.7	15.8±1.9	10.4±2.5
No	17.5±3.0	56.0±6.5	29.4±4.4	16.1±1.8	10.5±2.1
Number of Children ^b	S.rho=0.5; p=0.4	S.rho=0.03; p=0.6	S.rho=0.05; p=0.4	S.rho=0.1; p=0.07	S.rho=-0.09; p=0.1
Type of Nursing Home ^a	Z=-1.5; p=0.1	Z=-2.5; p=0.01	Z=-2.0; p=0.047	Z=-0.2; p=0.8	Z=-3.8; p<0.001
Public	17.3±2.8	56.5±6.6	29.6±4.5	16.1±1.9	10.8±2.2
Private	18.0±3.4	54.1±5.5	28.4±3.7	16.0±1.8	9.8±1.8
Duration of Stay at Nursing Home (year) ^b	S.rho=-0.1; p=0.2	S.rho=0.2; p=0.02	S.rho=0.08; p=0.2	S.rho=0.09; p=0.2	S.rho=0.2; p=0.001

^aMann-Whitney U Test, ^bSpearman's Correlation Analysis, ^cKruskal Wallis-H Test.

In the octogenarian group, a significant relationship was found between income level and the Detachment from Life (H=6.7; p<0.05) and Anger (H=10.0; p<0.05) subscales. Octogenarians with low income (16.7±1.8), moderate income (16.0±1.9), and high income (15.1±1.7), respectively, had higher mean scores in the Detachment from Life subscale, meanwhile, the mean scores for the Anger subscale were ranked as octogenarians with high income (11.8±2.9), low income (11.3±2.5), and moderate income (10.0±1.8).

It was observed that those residing in public nursing homes had higher mean scores for Suicide Probability (Z=-2.0; p<0.05) and Anger (Z=-2.6; p<0.05) compared to those residing in private nursing homes.

The risk status was determined using a cutoff score of 110 or higher for the Suicide Probability Scale, and a comparison was made between the octogenarian group and the other group consisting of individuals under 80 years of age. The

Table 3. Scale Scores of Octogenarians

Characteristics	Scales				
	Satisfaction with Life	Suicide Probability	Negative Self and Burnout	Detachment from Life	Anger
Gender ^a	Z=-0.3; p=0.8	Z=-2.2; p=0.03	Z=-1.3; p=0.2	Z=-2.6; p=0.009	Z=-1.8; p=0.07
Female	17.2±3.3	54.2±5.1	28.6±3.4	15.5±1.7	10.1±2.1
Male	17.3±3.2	57.1±6.9	29.9±4.7	16.5±2.0	10.7±2.2
Age ^b	S.rho=0.01; p=0.9	S.rho=-0.04; p=0.6	S.rho=-0.05; p=0.5	S.rho=-0.04; p=0.2	S.rho=0.02; p=0.8
Income Level ^c	H=0.2; p=0.9	H=4.1; p=0.1	H=0.6; p=0.8	H=6.7; p=0.03	H=10.0; p=0.007
Low	16.9±2.6	58.2±7.6	30.2±5.2	16.7±1.8	11.3±2.5
Moderate	17.4±3.4	55.3±5.9	29.3±4.0	16.0±1.9	10.0±1.8
High	16.9±3.3	56.0±5.8	29.1±4.0	15.1±1.7	11.8±2.9
Marital Status ^a	Z=-0.4; p=0.7	Z=-0.6; p=0.5	Z=-1.5; p=0.1	Z=-0.5; p=0.6	Z=-0.7; p=0.5
Unmarried	17.3±3.3	56.1±6.6	29.4±4.4	16.2±1.9	10.5±2.2
Married	16.8±2.5	56.6±5.2	30.6±3.6	16.1±1.9	9.9±1.5
Perception of Health ^c	H=1.8; p=0.4	H=0.2; p=0.9	H=0.6; p=0.7	H=0.9; p=0.6	H=2.6; p=0.3
Bad	16.9±3.4	57.2±6.6	28.9±4.0	16.4±1.8	11.9±2.9
Moderate	17.0±3.1	56.0±6.3	29.4±4.2	16.2±1.8	10.4±2.1
High	17.9±3.5	56.1±7.1	30.0±4.7	15.9±2.2	10.3±2.1
Chronic Illness ^a	Z=-0.4; p=0.7	Z=-0.6; p=0.5	Z=-1.5; p=0.1	Z=-0.5; p=0.6	Z=-0.7; p=0.5
Yes	17.4±3.2	55.8±6.0	29.2±3.9	16.2±1.9	10.5±2.3
No	16.8±3.2	57.1±7.7	30.5±5.5	16.1±2.1	10.5±1.8
Physical Disability ^a	Z=-1.0; p=0.3	Z=-0.9; p=0.4	Z=-0.8; p=0.5	Z=-0.03; p=1.0	Z=-0.7; p=0.5
Yes	16.4±2.2	54.9±5.8	28.6±3.7	16.1±1.9	10.2±2.1
No	17.4±3.3	56.3±6.6	29.6±4.4	16.2±1.9	10.5±2.2
Number of Children ^b	S.rho=0.1; p=0.2	S.rho=-0.04; p=0.7	S.rho=0.01; p=0.9	S.rho=0.2; p=0.8	S.rho=-0.09; p=0.3
Type of Nursing Home ^a	Z=-1.0; p=0.3	Z=-2.0; p=0.04	Z=-1.7; p=0.1	Z=-0.8; p=0.4	Z=-2.6; p=0.01
Public	17.0±2.9	56.8±6.7	29.9±4.5	16.2±2.0	10.7±2.1
Private	17.9±3.9	54.3±5.5	28.5±3.7	15.9±1.8	9.9±2.3
Duration of Stay at Nursing Home (year) ^b	S.rho=-0.1; p=0.2	S.rho=0.1; p=0.09	S.rho=0.08; p=0.3	S.rho=0.2; p=0.06	S.rho=0.1; p=0.1

^aMann-Whitney U Test, ^bSpearman's Correlation Analysis, ^cKruskal Wallis-H Test.

Table 4. Comparison of Octogenarians and the Other Group

Age Group ^a	Scales					
	Satisfaction with Life ^b		X/p	Suicide Probability ^b		X/p
	Below Median (<17)	Median and Above Median (≥17)		Low	High	
Octogenarian (≥80)	69 46.3%	80 53.7%	X=2.4;	147 98.7%	2 1.3%	X=0.4;
Other (<80)	69 55.6%	55 44.4%	p=0.08	121 97.6%	3 2.4%	p=0.4

^aChi-square Test, ^bRun (Swed-Eisenhart) Test.

analysis conducted between these two groups did not reveal a significant difference ($X=0.4$; $p>0.05$). Additionally, scores obtained from the Satisfaction With Life Scale were grouped according to the median value, and no significant difference was found between the octogenarian group and the other group ($X=2.4$ $p>0.05$).

DISCUSSION

This study aims to emphasize the significance of suicide among elderly individuals and examines the risk factors for suicide in the elderly. Previous research has indicated that although suicides among elderly individuals may not receive as much attention as those of young adults, suicide rates increase with age, with the highest rates observed in elderly males (Crestani et al. 2019). Advanced age, male gender, living alone, psychiatric disorders, bereavement, and physical illnesses are identified as risk factors for suicide in the elderly (Fox et al. 2017). It is noted that the elderly may be more determined and less impulsive in their suicide attempts, and physical vulnerability, chronic illnesses, and social isolation can contribute to the mortality by suicide attempts (Cattell 2000). Additionally, it is reported that a significant majority of those who die by suicide have been diagnosed with at least one major psychiatric disorder (Shah and Buckley 2011).

Octogenarians, who are individuals aged 80 and above, constitute a group particularly at risk of suicide. This research aims to understand the factors influencing the likelihood of suicide in octogenarians. This study is considered valuable for being the first study to focus on the “octogenarian” age group in Turkish psychiatric literature and to investigate suicidal ideation in this age group in the international literature.

In this section, the analysis results that examine the correlation between the socio-demographic characteristics of the elderly participants and the dependent variables are explained.

When the findings of this study are evaluated for the elderly, it is observed that the results obtained are similar with other studies in the literature. A significant relationship was found only in the Anger subscale among dependent variables with gender, indicating that male participants had higher anger score averages than females. A study conducted by Birditt and Fingerman in 2003 also found that elderly males had higher levels of anger than elderly females (Birditt and Fingerman 2003).

As for the relationship between income level and dependent variables, a significant difference was found in the Suicide Probability main scale and the Detachment from Life and Anger subscales which affect the main scale. This indicates that elderly individuals with low and high income obtained

higher scores in these scales. Regardless of income level, economic uncertainty experienced has globally reinforced suicidal thoughts. The lower mean scores for individuals with moderate income are interpreted as a result of economic stability. An ecological study also supports this idea (Er et al. 2023). Moreover, O'Connor and Pirkis (2016) also support this finding in terms of the impact of income level on the suicide risk in the elderly. Another study conducted on the elderly individuals residing in nursing homes in Manisa revealed that elderly individuals perceiving their socioeconomic status as low or moderate were associated with depression (Demet et al. 2002).

A weak relationship was observed between the duration of staying in the nursing home and the Suicide Probability main scale and the Anger subscale. Furthermore, it was observed that elderly individuals who stayed longer in the nursing home had higher anger scores. A study by Aydemir (1999) draws attention to the increasing rate of suicides in elderly individuals. Changes in societal structures and family dynamics have led elderly individuals into social isolation, increasing the risk of depression and suicide. Moreover, with the prolongation of life expectancy, the importance of home support services for elderly individuals living alone is emphasized (Aydemir 1999). In a study comparing nursing homes and home environment, it was found that elderly individuals residing in nursing homes had a higher frequency of depression compared to elderly individuals living at home (Maral et al. 2001). Another study stated that the crowded environment in nursing homes made it difficult for the elderly individuals to adapt to life and highlighted the need for the improvement of home care services (Aközer et al. 2011).

A significant relationship was found between the type of nursing home and the Suicide Probability main scale, as well as the Negative Self and Burnout, and Anger subscales that affect the main scale. It was determined that the mean scores for Suicide Probability, Negative Self and Burnout, and Anger were higher for those residing in public nursing homes compared to those in private nursing homes. This finding can pave the way for future studies.

The findings of this study are consistent with other studies on similar topics and demonstrate that sociodemographic factors can be associated with dependent variables in elderly individuals. However, when the results of the in-depth analyses focusing on the octogenarian (80 years and older) age group are thoroughly reviewed, significant relationships have been identified between gender and the Suicide Probability main scale, the Detachment from Life subscale, and the Anger subscale.

When examining the relationship between the Suicide Probability main scale and gender, it was observed that

males had higher mean scores than females. This indicates that elderly octogenarian males are at a higher risk of suicide probability. Similarly, for Detachment from Life and Anger subscales, mean scores of the males were also higher than those of females. These findings suggest that males experience more detachment from life and have higher levels of anger during late adulthood. A study conducted in 2011 also found higher suicide rates in elderly octogenarian males compared to females (Conwell et al. 2011). Another study conducted in 2005 in Manisa province among individuals aged between 18-65 found that females had more suicidal thoughts and attempts than males, however, different results can also be obtained due to the fact that the study sample consisted of young adults, Manisa province gained metropolitan status in 2012 and rapidly industrialized (Deveci et al. 2005).

The relationship between income level, another independent variable, and the Detachment from Life and Anger subscales of octogenarians was examined. When the mean scores of octogenarians with low, medium, and high incomes on the Detachment from Life subscale were examined, it was observed that individuals with low income had higher scores. Similarly, when the mean scores on the Anger subscale were examined, individuals with high income had lower scores. These results indicate that octogenarians with low income levels experience a lack of attachment to life and have higher levels of anger. As a result, it was found that octogenarians residing in public nursing homes had higher Suicide Probability and Anger scores compared to those residing in private nursing homes. These two findings indicate an inverse relationship between income status and suicide probability and anger levels in octogenarians.

These findings demonstrate that factors such as gender, income level, and the type of nursing home significantly influence the psychological states of elderly individuals in the octogenarian age group. Further research is needed, and these factors should be applied to a broader elderly population. This study also emphasizes the importance of separately addressing the octogenarian age group within the elderly population.

The strong aspect of this research is that it improves the clinical awareness about octogenarians, one of the most vulnerable populations of society, and suicides, which is an important public health problem, thus establishing a reference point for studies to be conducted in the future.

It is established that in older individuals, even subclinical morphometric changes in the brain that do not cause symptoms can trigger suicidal ideation with the advancement of age. The limitation of this study can be the absence of neuroimaging evaluations (Cao et al. 2023). Additionally, it is believed that multi-center, large-scale future studies with mixed methods which show effort to increase group

homogeneity and include individual differences within the study will contribute to the literature.

CONCLUSION

The risk of suicide among the elderly is a matter that should not be overlooked. Octogenarians represent a population group at risk of suicide, and sociodemographic factors such as gender, income level, and the type of nursing home can impact this risk. These findings support the development of further protective and preventive strategies to maintain the psychological well-being of the elderly individuals and prevent completed suicide cases. In this context, it is crucial to expand psychological support services among the elderly, reduce social isolation, and establish programs to assist them in coping with economic challenges. Furthermore, mental health professionals, families, and society should approach the psychological needs of the elderly in a more sensitive manner.

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Acknowledgments: *We would like to express our gratitude to the employees of Manisa Provincial Directorate of Family and Social Services who supported this study, as well as to all the elderly participants.*